

ISic3690

I.Sicily inscription 3690

Language

Latin

Type**Material**

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Uncertain; Mommsen thought Urban, Korhonen thinks local

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][IOVII][---]

2. [---Ca]ecilia[---]

3. [---]issj,ṃa [---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae*

Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 06.1379 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione*. Helsinki. At 64

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